

University Education as a Veritable Tool for Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria: A Theoretical Review

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Article History:

Received: 01.02.2025 Revised: 25.02.2025 Accepted: 27.02.2025 Published: 28.02.2025

Abstract

University education is widely regarded as a catalyst for economic growth and social transformation. This theoretical study critically examines the role of university education as a veritable tool for poverty alleviation in Nigeria; drawing insights from Walt Rostow's (1960) Modernization Theory. The study conceptualizes poverty as a multidimensional challenge that limits economic and human development. It further explores how university curricula, designed to equip graduates with relevant skills and knowledge, contribute to poverty reduction. In addition, the study highlights the role of university community services in empowering local populations and fostering economic development. The impact of university research in addressing socio-economic challenges and providing innovative solutions to poverty-related issues is also discussed. However, the study identifies several constraints, including inadequate funding, outdated curricula, weak industry-academia collaboration, and infrastructural deficits; which hinder universities from effectively fulfilling their poverty alleviation roles. The paper concludes that while Nigerian universities have the potential to drive economic transformation, significant reforms are needed to enhance their impact. Suggestions include improved funding, curriculum restructuring to emphasize entrepreneurship and vocational skills, and stronger policy support for university-led community and research initiatives.

Keywords: *University Education, Veritable Tool, Poverty, Poverty Alleviation, Theoretical Review.*

Suggested citation: Oguejiofor, C.N., Okafor, J.N., Chigbu, B.C., Ezenwagu, S.A., Mokwe, N.F., & Okechukwu, J.N. (2025). University Education as a Veritable Tool for Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria: A Theoretical Review. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 104-114. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).08)

Introduction

Globally, education is regarded as one of the most important investments a country can make for her socio-economic and political transformation. This is premised on the ability of education to make individuals become proactive, secure firm control over their lives and widen their range of available options. In this regard, disparity in the development between developed and developing nations has been linked with education. This is perhaps why different countries accord recognition to education by investing heavily in this sub-sector. The United Nations Educational and Scientific Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020) considered education to be a basic human right and it is closely related to development in all segments which includes social and human development. In Nigeria, education is perceived as a veritable tool for national development. This position is amplified in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) where it is explicitly stated that education shall continue to be highly rated in the national development plans because education is the most important instrument of change; any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by educational revolution.

University education is a critical component of human development worldwide. It provides trained individuals, who develop the capacity and analytical skills that drive local economies and are responsible for important decisions which affect every society. The university is the apex institution of higher education in Nigeria and has its own specific roles. Three of the major principal functions of universities include teaching, research and dedicated services to the community through extra-mural and extension services. In order to realize these objectives, the Federal Government of Nigeria has always been

linking up the establishment of universities in Nigeria with various development plans. The Global University Network for Innovation (GUNI) (as cited in Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2019) in a study consulted 214 key experts in higher education including university leaders, policy-makers and other social agents from 80 countries, to obtain their views on the principal trends, issues and opinions related to the new challenges and emerging roles of higher education in human and social development throughout the world. The results of the poll showed that the vast majority of international experts believed that higher education must play an active role in facilitating human and social development. Participants identified several priority issues, including the reduction of poverty, sustainable development, the incorporation of critical thought and ethical values into the globalization process, and the improvement of governability and participatory democracy. A critical examination of the opinion of these key experts in higher education and policy makers, indicate an enormous responsibility for Nigerian universities. It was against this background that an attempt was made to determine the extent to which Nigerian universities have contributed to poverty alleviation in Nigeria through teaching, research and community service.

The Concept of Poverty

The definition of poverty varies widely and different criteria have been used to conceptualize poverty by different authors. Poverty is viewed by many analysts as a state of insufficient income and abject deprivation of life's basic necessities. Some others have defined poverty in terms of level of education, health and environment and so on. Salami and Afolabi (2022) explained poverty as a state of being where we are unable to meet our needs. These

basic needs include food, health, education and shelter. According to Eze and Okoye (2018), poverty curtails the capabilities of an individual. This implies that an individual lacks the freedom to achieve or meet his needs. Boateng (2021) described poverty as a human condition characterized by sustained or chronic deprivation of the resources, capabilities, choices, security and power necessary for enjoyment of an adequate standard of living and other civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights. Poverty could be structural or temporary. Structural poverty may be explained as state of being where an individual is persistently deprived of the basic needs of life which may have been caused by the lack of possession of minimum relevant skills for gainful employment. It could also be as a result of cultural, religious or socio-political factors (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund [UNICEF], 2023). Temporary poverty as the name implies is transient which could be linked to natural causes and man's imperfections.

Poverty in Nigeria remains significant despite seemingly high economic growth. Statistics indicate that the number of those in poverty has been on the increase. Uche and Okafor (2019) noted that those living in poverty in Nigeria have increased from 27% in 1980 to 46% in 1985 and to 67% in 1996; in 1999 it has increased to 70%, and by 2020 has increased to more than 80%. Indeed, the latest available data, Nigeria ranks 163rd out of 191 countries on the United Nations Development Programme's (UNDP) Human Development Index (HDI) for 2021/2022 with HDI of 0.40 among the poorest countries. Millenium Summit (2020) also named Nigeria as one of the leading third world nations in which a good proportion of the world's poorest live. These indexes assess countries based on life expectancy, education, and per capita income. Nigeria's position reflects significant challenges in these areas. In terms of multidimensional poverty, the 2022 Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) report indicates that 63% of Nigerians (approximately 133 million people) are multidimensionality poor. This means they experience multiple deprivations across health,

education, living standards, and work. The report also highlights regional disparities, with higher poverty levels in the northern regions compared to the southern parts of the country. These findings underscore the critical need for targeted interventions to address the various dimensions of poverty in Nigeria. However, the issue of poverty eradication has been a major concern of successive governments and institutions in Nigeria as well as other developing countries in the world where poverty has become pandemic, (Zubair & Lawal, 2023). Government in an effort to alleviate poverty has initiated a number of programmes. The latest of this is 'The National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP). This programme which was established in 2001 is aimed at improving the skills of the less privileged in the society, as a basis for eradicating poverty in various communities. The latest among these programmes include the National Social Investment Programmes (NSIP), which encompass N-Power, Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT), Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP), and the Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSF), alongside recent World Bank-supported initiatives for education, healthcare, and sustainable power. Nonetheless, poverty is increasing in the country due to factors like unemployment, the widening gap between the rich and the poor, corruption and poor leadership.

Theoretical Framework

Modernization Theory by Walt Rostow in 1960

The study was anchored on the Modernization Theory propounded by Walt Rostow in 1960. The theory presents economic development as a linear process in which societies progress through five distinct stages: traditional society, preconditions for takeoff, takeoff, drives to maturity, and age of high mass consumption. Rostow argued that economic growth is driven by industrialization, technological advancement, and institutional reforms; emphasizing the role of education in fostering modern values such as innovation, rationality, and productivity. This theory suggests that less-developed countries,

like Nigeria, can achieve economic prosperity by adopting Western-style development strategies; including investment in higher education, infrastructure, and market-driven policies. Education, particularly university education, is seen as a critical enabler of modernization that equips individuals with skills, knowledge, and entrepreneurial capabilities needed for national transformation. Applying Modernization Theory to the study of university education as a tool for poverty alleviation in Nigeria, the theory underscores the role of higher education in transitioning societies from underdevelopment to economic prosperity. University education enhances human capital by equipping graduates with technical and professional skills that increase employability, entrepreneurship, and innovation; thereby fostering economic growth. In line with Rostow's model, university education aligns with the "preconditions for takeoff" and "takeoff" stages, where knowledge-driven policies and technological advancements spur industrialization and productivity. By producing skilled graduates who can drive innovation and industry, universities serve as catalysts for Nigeria's transition from a resource-dependent economy to a knowledge-based and technologically advanced society.

The relevance of Modernization Theory to university education in Nigeria is evident in its emphasis on knowledge diffusion, research, and human capital development, all of which are crucial for poverty alleviation. A strong university system fosters socio-economic mobility by reducing inequalities in access to quality education which breaks the cycle of poverty. Moreover, higher education promotes modern economic sectors such as information technology, engineering, and business, which are critical for national development. Modernization Theory remains a suitable framework for analyzing the transformative potential of university education in alleviating poverty in Nigeria. The theory highlights the need for investment in human capital development as a prerequisite for economic modernization; aligning with global trends where higher education is a key driver of national progress. While Nigeria must adapt modernization strategies to its unique socio-economic realities,

strengthening university education through improved funding, curriculum reform, and industry partnerships can accelerate economic development and poverty reduction. Thus, Modernization Theory provides a theoretical foundation for understanding how university education can be leveraged to achieve sustainable development and social empowerment in Nigeria.

University Curricular and Poverty Alleviation

The National Policy on Education became operational in Nigeria in 1982. The rationale for the policy according to Ibukun and Aboliwodi (as cited in Salami & Afolabi, 2022) was the observed irrelevant nature of Nigeria's existing system of education inherited from Britain. The colonial education system was exotic and bookish and placed emphasis on the production of an elite group that shunned manual and practical work. The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013) stated among others that university education is expected to make optimum contribution to national development by intensifying its programmes for the development of high level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation. Osarumwense (2014) noted that universities all over the world are currently immersed in one of the most interesting and challenging periods in their history as they remain the key institutions in producing and disseminating knowledge and constitute the backbone of economic and social development. Adebayo Ogunleye (2019) clarified that university education is responsible for training future professionals who will occupy strategic positions in society and the labour market.

Nonetheless, Eze and Okoye (2018) noted that even though the content of Nigeria's education curricular kept changing, the structure and practice remained stagnant. Oke et al. (2020) in agreement with Eze and Okoye (2018) remarked that most university dons in Nigerian universities are disconnected academics producing white elephant curricular for use in various faculties leading to the production of white collar graduates whose qualifications are not defensible in the labour market. There

appears to be an apparent disparity or mis-match between what is produced by the universities (graduates) and what is needed in the labour market. Ibrahim and Mohammed (2021) observed that there is considerable concern about graduate unemployment, but no one has any idea about which graduate is unemployed, why and where, so that universities may appropriately adjust their intake into various courses they offer. Nwosu and Chukwuma (2020) remarked that this has led to a great army of unemployable graduates that are churned out annually from the universities with qualifications and certificates that are not usable or marketable.

Commenting on this problem, Oke et al. (2024) stated that employers complained that skills of Nigerian graduates had steadily declined between 2010 and 2022 and have become increasingly unproductive. Ogunyemi and Olatunji (2018) also noted that there have been reports on denial of Nigerian graduates into direct admission for postgraduate degree courses in foreign universities due to their reservation about the quality of university education in Nigeria. An unemployed individual depends on another to survive; thereby perpetuating poverty. Uche and Okafor (2019) observed that the unemployed youths whose ages range between 18 and 25 usually embark on pointless existence on petty crime and anti-social behavior that can end only in life-long welfare dependency or serial offending. The United States Agency for International Development (USAID, 2019) argued that the struggle against poverty, improved standard of living and overall development of a nation, that quality education particularly at the university level is the key. Consequently university education plays a fundamental and decisive role in transferring the knowledge, values and skills that it imparts into the public domain (International Monetary Fund [IMF], 2023). It behooves therefore that if the Nigerian university education fails to equip its graduates with skills that guarantee employability then the fight against poverty is already lost. Thus Nigerian university system rather than being a source of economic progression that transforms and empowers the citizens of the country appears to have impoverished its graduates. This is because rather than equip

them with relevant skills and knowledge to be job creators, most of them are job seekers.

The obvious disconnect between university programmes and what is required in the labour market and the perceived low quality of the Nigerian university graduate by foreign universities may not be unconnected to the university curricular and pedagogical processes; which are obsolete and therefore not relevant to the challenges of today's workplace and serious academic pursuit. The apparent deficiency in skill acquisition by the graduates discourage employers from engaging them as they (the employers) bear the cost of their training and retraining so that they can fit into organizations. The graduates also lack the skills that will make them employers of labour themselves or self-employed. Education can only bring about poverty eradication and sustainable nation building if its educated and skilled individuals are able to secure placement in the labour market or self-reliant by setting up their own businesses. In response to the agitation for more practical courses in the universities in order to ensure employability after graduation, the Nigeria Universities Commission (NUC) introduced a compulsory entrepreneurial course for all undergraduates. This programme took effect from the 2007/2008 academic session.

The impact of this programme is yet to be felt as it appears to exist only on paper as most universities have not effectively implemented it. This is apparent from the large number of graduates who are still unemployed despite having gone through the programme. Ogundari and Aromolaran (2014) explained that government initiatives for higher education reform should focus on ensuring that universities respond to the needs of their societies and provide a platform upon which countries can base their competitiveness in the context of globalization. They opined that the fundamental mission of these institutions should cover national requirements against a background of serious problems such as poverty, environmental degradation, terrorism, disease and ongoing national conflicts. As mentioned earlier, one of the principal functions of universities is community service. It is pertinent at this juncture to examine the extent

you which this function has been successfully performed by the universities.

University Community Service and Poverty Alleviation

Policy makers in developed economies are increasingly viewing colleges and universities as engines of local economic development in the fight against poverty. Questions have continually been raised on ways in which universities can extend the results of education and research to the development of the society as a whole. According to Bilenkisi et al. (2015) the success stories of places like Silicon Valley and Boston's Route 128 in the United States of America are driving this trend of how academic institutions tend to bring stability to area economies. This policy stipulates that colleges and universities can contribute to the economic success of their community by deepening the skills and knowledge or human capital of its residence. One way this is achieved is by producing graduates who join the community's educated force; thereby increasing the human capital level. In addition, the knowledge and technologies created through research activities at the universities may not only attract new firms to the community but also help existing businesses expand and innovate (Gounder & Xing, 2012). What this entails largely is that the universities can help build the knowledge and skills (human capital) of its local community. This critical component of a community's economic success can be positively affected by the university through the organization of seminars and workshops for residents in order to disseminate information from relevant research findings, aimed at specific economic activities. Indeed a community with higher levels of human capital tends to have greater amounts of economic activity and more rapid economic growth. A recent study by Zubair and Lawal (2023) established a causal link between human capital and local economic activity.

The implication of this to the nation is that university education institutions should aim to help the communities around them by directly

transmitting knowledge and experience. Universities in Nigeria therefore need to produce graduates with skills that are relevant to the economies of their local community. For instance, universities that are cited in the Lagos area will have to produce graduates with high level skills in fishing and vegetable production which is the dominant economic activity of Lagosians. In addition the universities need to organize workshops, seminars and practical lessons for the local farmers on new ways of improving production in these areas as well as giving the farmers new and improved seedlings to increase their yields. When people increase the knowledge of their primary economic activity, it goes further to enhance productivity and promote growth (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2022). Increase in productivity translates to increased income which ultimately eradicates poverty. If indeed, Nigerian universities engage in the human capital development of their local communities; the multiplier effect is unimaginable as the effect of the "knowledge spillovers" - the transfer of knowledge and skills from one individual to another is unquantifiable. Poverty and its attendant effects on the Nigerian nation will be a thing of the past.

University Research and Poverty Alleviation

The role of university research in national development and eradication of poverty cannot be overemphasized. Research is the process of proffering solutions to human problems through well-defined methods. It is a systematic process of resolving human problems based on knowledge. Research leads to development and development eliminates poverty. There has been a steady and systematic decline in the quality and quantity of university research since the late 1980's up to date. Pervez (2014) noted that in terms of quality and quantity, the research output of tertiary institutions in Nigeria was about the best in Sub-Saharan Africa up to the late 1980's. However, Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) were of the opinion that by 2006, the quantity and quality of research had declined to an all-time low. Some of the reasons attributed for this decline ranged from lack of research skills in the modern methods, constraints of equipment for

carrying out state-of-the-art research, overloaded teaching and administrative schedules which leave little time for research, difficulty in accessing research funds to diminishing scope of mentoring junior researchers by seasoned and senior researcher due to brain drain (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2022).

Apart from the decline in quality and quantity of university research, it has been observed that there has been a disconnect between Nigerian university research and the productive sectors of the economy. According to Uche and Okafor (2019) research has been trapped in and limited by the immediate idiosyncrasies of supervisors and graduates. There is little or no evidence of the impact of university research on local economies and not much is heard or known about licensing of university-owned patents by the industries in Nigeria. Janjua and Kamal (2011) observed that research capabilities with no clear social direction or supervision, and isolated from other basic aspects of social and moral responsibility cannot fulfill their potentials for improving the quality of life of the general population. University research is supposed to act as channels of technology transfer and also contribute to the local economy through the entrepreneurial efforts of their graduates. Another way by which university research engenders national development and poverty alleviation is by stimulating corporate research and development (R&D) activity. Much of the breakthroughs and innovations in the advanced economies originated from researches carried out in the universities. It is no wonder therefore, that Nigeria is still at the crawling stage of technological advancement and development which can easily be traced to the gap between research in our universities and the nation's economy.

Educational Management Universities can also concentrate on the production of skilled labours for the local industries. For instance, universities in Lagos area can help local businesses grow through their research activities and new technologies to enhance their productivity (Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2019). This connection between academic research and local business activity can take many forms. One is when local businesses use university knowledge and

research facilities to create products and services. This will result in increase in job availability for skilled and unskilled labour. Ogundari and Aromolaran (2014) noted that universities in developing countries must produce their own competitive research and act as dependable social agents; which entails responding to the needs of the people that they represent and taking an active role in the fight for human rights and social justice.

Constraints to the Universities in Fulfilling these Roles

The universities in Nigeria contend with a lot of issues that prevent them from operating at the same level with their counterparts in the world in the fight against poverty. They are hereby discussed under the following headings: obsolete curricular, shortage of infrastructure, inadequate funding, brain-drain syndrome, disconnection with the private sector/policy makers, and lack of university autonomy.

Obsolete Curricular

In spite of the lofty goals of education as stated in the National Policy on Education, the quality of Nigerian graduates has been on the decline and many remain unemployed. It has also been established that there is disparity between the labour market demand and the products of the universities. Emphasis has been on producing graduates who require 'white collar jobs' rather than on self-reliant graduates. The university curriculum which is largely theoretical rather than equipping the students with skills that will enable them to be self-employed or employers of labour themselves have turned them to job seekers. Even though the NUC has made the teaching of entrepreneurial skills compulsory in the universities, its implementation has been a herculean task for most universities (Osarumwense, 2014). Like most other policies in Nigeria, it appears that the teaching staff were not prepared for its take-off and the provision of building and equipment for the centres for skill acquisition in the universities were not also ready. In addition to this, is the failure to streamline the existing curriculum to accommodate the entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme and also delineating the

available skills to meet the needs and aspirations of students from the various university departments (Eze & Okoye, 2018). Even though the entrepreneurial skill acquisition programme will bridge the gap between school and work, a lot of work still needs to be done to successfully implement it.

Shortage of Infrastructure

The most important activity that takes place in any university is teaching and learning. For quality learning to take place, the physical infrastructure which includes classroom, lecture theatres, well- equipped laboratories, workshops among others have to be adequate (World Bank, 2018). The quantitative growth of Nigerian universities over the years have not been matched by corresponding expansion of facilities and equipment to cater for the large prospective students' population and the large number of those already in school. Oke et al. (2020) observed that inadequate provision of physical facilities implies that there is a mismatch between the students' population and physical facilities such as classrooms, lecture theatres, laboratories, studios and seats for students. They noted that when physical facilities are inadequate, there is the problem of overcrowding with its corresponding negative impact on available space for meaningful learning. Osarumwense (2014) reported that access to higher education and the lack of the capacity of the system to absorb the numbers of the students seeking admission to higher education institutions continues to pose a serious problem. Ibrahim and Mohammed, (2021) reported that according to Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (J. A.M.B.) out of about 1,200,000 candidates that sat for the 2021 examination, only 247,000 would be offered places in the existing universities. This represents only 20.58 percent. According to Osarumwense (2014), only 5.2 percent to 15.3 percent of the thousands of candidates who apply for admission into tertiary institutions are given admission each year. The report of the presidential visitation panel which looked into the operations of all federal universities between 2009 and 2023 revealed that the academic and physical facilities at all the universities were in deplorable states with insufficient lecture

theatres/halls, laboratories among others (NUC, 2024). In addition to the lack of adequate infrastructure to accommodate new students is the poor state of the existing ones. Adebayo and Ogunleye (2019) reported that lecture halls, laboratories, students' hostels, library space, books, journals and office space are in short supply in Nigerian universities. According to Eze and Okoye (2018), the inadequacy of such physical resources like classrooms, laboratories, libraries and other academic resources translates to poor results.

Inadequate Funding

Universities throughout the world are increasingly being asked to maintain their key functions in the face of budget restrictions; which lead to a deterioration in the level of service offered. It seems that there is neither the time nor the money that would enable universities to consider new approaches to education or social environment. In this climate, universities with extensive research programmes have been most adversely affected by the need to find new sources of funding, and have found themselves forced to modify their operational structures considerably. Ibrahim and Mohammed (2021) noted that the Nigerian government over the years has not been meeting the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) recommendation of 26 percent of the total budget allocation to education sector. Indeed, Ogunyemi and Olatunji (2018) argued that the major challenge facing the management of university system in Nigeria is inadequate funding. The effect of poor funding according to Nwosu and Chukwuma (2020) is more visible in the areas of faculty salaries, libraries, equipment, research and quality of students entering our universities today. Statistics from Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) shows that in 2000, education budget was 8.36% of the nation's total budget; in 2011, 9.30%; 2012, 9.86%; 2013, 10.10%; 2014, 10.50%; 2015, 10.70%; 2016, 7.90%; 2017, 7.40%; 2018, 7.04%; 2019, 7.05%; 2020, 6.70%; 2021, 5.60%; 2022, 7.20%; and in 2023, 8.20%. The apparent imbalance between funds available to the universities and what is required to effectively run the university system is largely responsible for their deplorable state. The

deplorable state of the infrastructure in the nation's universities has always been cited as one of the reasons for the incessant strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU).

Erosion of Autonomy

Zubair and Lawal (2023) defined university autonomy as protection of the universities from interference by government and its agencies in the administration of the universities; notably in such areas as student selection, content and programmes of university education, staff recruitment and appointment, and so on. Government interference is equally observable in the appointment and removal of principal officers of the university such as the vice chancellor and academic staff. Ogunyemi and Olatunji (2018) observed that:

universities suffered from arbitrary governance.... Rather than being a place where justice and truth are nurtured, the universities triumphed in mediocrity and untruths. Promotion was earned through sycophancy and the admission procedure became systematically bastardized as wives, children and the cronies of vice-chancellors had their own admission quota without reference to the established procedures. University governance became unpredictable and university finance in shambles.

According to Ibrahim and Mohammed (2021), between 1992 and 1998, sole administrators were appointed for the following Nigerian universities: Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, (ABU), University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN), Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUT), University of Maiduguri, Ladoke Akintola University (LAUTECH) Ogbomoso, and Edo State University, Ekpoma. Babarinde (as cited in Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2019) captured the state of Nigerian universities in this way:

...the recent attack on the Nigerian intellectual community by the Federal Government of Nigeria through refusal to honour agreement with the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), support to the arbitrary sacking of lecturers at the university of Ilorin, attempts to force arbitrary rule on universities through Federal Government sponsored. Autonomy Bill and when that failed, another attempt to jettison already passed and

assented Bill which did not contain government positions. The attitude of President Obasanjo administration towards the Academic Staff Union of Universities in particular and all trade unions in general are evidences of lack of academic freedom and institutional autonomy... Most federal and state universities depend on government subvention for survival and as the popular saying goes: he who pays the piper dictates the tune.

Disparity between University Research and the Nigerian Economy

One of the primary roles of the university globally in poverty alleviation is to build and develop its host community. One way is usually through the production of students that will fit into the economic activities of the community. Secondly, is by carrying out researches aimed at improving the output of farming and industrial activities of that community. Uche and Okafor (2019) noted that this practice is more common in North America where students participating in community engagement programmes undertake placements in companies or other organizations in the immediate community. Many students believe that these placements are beneficial to their academic courses and professional growth. However, there appears to be a disconnect between the researches carried out in the Nigerian universities and the economy of the nation as well as a major decline in the quality of research. According to Osarumwense (2014), over 99.5% if not 100% of the Nigerian university activity and time are devoted to teaching and assessing of students throughout the year, without definite time designated for doing research. Funding of research activities has also been a major constraint. A survey conducted revealed that less than 10% of the academic staff in the Nigerian universities received research grants in the past one and half decades (NUC, Research Bulletin, 2007 - 2020). Poor communication between the universities and the industries as well as poor and indifferent attitudes to university research by the productive sector seem to be militating against the effective use and application of university research to economic development and poverty eradication. Pervez (2014) observed that in many cases globally, the insularity of higher education institutions has isolated them from new practice-

based sources of knowledge; particularly social movements, civil security organizations, groups of experts on various aspects of human and social development.

Brain-drain Syndrome

The past few decades have witnessed the gradual but steady exodus of many academic staff from the universities in Nigeria to other sectors of the economy and to overseas universities in search of the proverbial Golden Fleece. Zubair and Lawal (2023) remarked that there was mass exodus of many brilliant lecturers that could not compete on political campus arena from the university campus while some left to join the rat race in the business world and still some others left Nigeria for better services. According to Yusuf and Afolabi (2022), between 2008 and 2022, over 2000 lecturers left the federal university system in Nigeria. Gounder and Xing (2012) opined that the relatively low level of academic salaries in comparison to other sectors, high staff/student ratio, increased workload among others are responsible for this phenomenon.

Conclusion

There is a universal concern on the issue of poverty alleviation with university education seen as playing a pivotal role in curbing the menace. There are however constraints that are likely to prevent Nigerian universities from effectively performing this role. These problems are not insurmountable provided the various key stakeholders in the education sector work together to provide quality and functional education and also discharge their duties effectively and efficiently.

Suggestions

Based on the observable challenges confronting Nigerian universities in the area of poverty alleviation, the following suggestions are made:

1. Universities must ensure constant review of curricular in line with the dynamics of the society.
2. Entrepreneurial education should be incorporated into the academic programmes in the universities.
3. There should be effective collaboration between universities and organized private sector to ensure that quality of graduates meet the needs of the labour market. University curricular should reflect the demand of the labour market..
4. The universities need to be adequately funded in order to consummate various functions relevant to poverty alleviation.
5. Management of universities must embark on aggressive internally generated revenue to minimize absolute dependence on government.
6. Universities should be accorded greater autonomy as this is inimical to their survival.
7. Research in the universities should be in collaboration with local industries to solve existing problems and also improve productivity in identified areas
8. Establishment of Research Universities is advocated as they play a pivotal role in organizing a research system to generate capability for augmenting a national productive power.
9. To stem the tide of faculty exodus, the remuneration of university lecturers and conditions of service should be attractive and at par with other sectors of the economy.

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